

Research Article

CLASS-CHANGING DERIVATIONAL
AFFIXES

Morphology

Keywords: Prefixes, Suffixes, Derivational, Word, Conversion, etc.

Arburim Iseni

Associate Professor. State University of Tetovo. Faculty of Philology.
Department of English Language and Literature. North Macedonia

Abstract

Morphology is the study of a word's grammatical constituents. The many different methods that English words are formed, including borrowing from Latin and Greek, clipping, suppletion, affixation, conversion, acronym, blending, compounding, and more, have been documented by linguists. The goal of this study is to examine the process of word formation known as affixation, specifically class-changing derivational affixation. We will examine the meanings of some of the few letters added to the beginning or end of words as well as the changes that occur when affixes are inserted into words. This study aims to examine how different affixes are added to the beginning or end of a root or root word to create new words, as well as how those affixes alter the root word's classification. A list of English prefixes and suffixes that change the class are provided, and they are explained and studied with various examples. The derivation of words from one grammatical class to another is observed in this study. For example, verbs are converted into nouns and adjectives, nouns are converted into adjectives and verbs, and so on.

Introduction

The stem word, or root, from which most English words are derived, holds the essence of the meaning of each word. Affixes are placed at the beginning or end of certain words to make them longer. Affixation is the term used to describe the act of adding certain affixes. Prefix and suffix are terms used to describe the affixes added to words, respectively, at the beginning and end of the root. The root plays a crucial role in the formation of new words.

A morphological process called affixation involves joining a bound morpheme, or affix, to a morphological foundation. In the field of morphology, affixation falls under the heading of bound morphemes, which can be either roots or affixes. The most frequent affix types across linguistic boundaries are prefixes (affixes that come before the root) and suffixes (affixes that come after the root). Affixation is the most popular method used by human languages to create new words and word forms. Affixes indicate derivational changes (such as the *-er* in *teach-er*) and inflectional changes (such as the *-s* in *teacher-s*). However, languages differ in the ways they express the same semantics. For example in English the noun *biolog-ist* is derived from *biology* by adding the suffix *-ist*. Most languages employ affixes extensively (most European, African, Australian, and Amerindian languages fall into this category), although some, like Vietnamese, don't use them at all. There is a widespread preference for suffixes over prefixes in languages that use affixes.

Roots and Stems

As previously indicated, roots and stems, the morphemes, whether free or bound, that carry a word's primary or fundamental concept, idea, or meaning are called roots (or bases). They

typically serve as the foundation or core of words. When roots are free morphemes, they can stand alone as content (and function) words, as in the words *carry*, *quick*, *early*, *book*, *dog*, *house*, etc. When morphemes from roots are joined together, they create word components like *-ceive* in *perceive*, *-ment* in *achievement*, *-sume* in *presume*, etc. Stems, on the other hand, are free roots that have already received or will presumably get derivational affixes. According to this definition, a stem is the combination of a root and one or more derivations, such as *comfortable*, *uncomfortable*, or *accountableness*. Stems are words that lack inflectional morphemes, as you can see. For instance, the stems in the phrase *disestablishment* are *disestablish*, *establishment*, and *establish* (which is also a root).

Types of Affixes

Affixes can be categorized in two ways: based on where they appear in a word and based on what they do in a phrase or sentence.

1. Affixes are divided into *prefixes*, *infixes*, and *suffixes* depending on where they are located within the word (or side of the word they are attached to).

2. *Affixes are divided into derivational affixes* (derivational morphemes or derivations) and *inflectional affixes* based on the function they serve in the language (inflectional morphemes or inflections).

Prefix

A prefix is an affix that comes before the word stem. When it is introduced at the beginning, it changes one word into another. An example of a prefix is “*anti-*,” which means “*against*,” “*co-*,” which means “*with*,” “*mis-*,” which means “*wrong*” or “*bad*,” and “*trans-*,” which means “*across*.” Prefixes are added to the beginning of a word to help partially communicate its meaning.

For example, when the prefix *un-* is added to the word *joyous*, the word *unhappy* is formed. A prefix is also known as a preformative, particularly in the study of languages, because it modifies the form of the words to which it is attached.

The most common negative prefixes in English are “*a-*” in the word *amoral*, “*in-*” in the word *incapable*, and “*un-*” in the word *unable*. While other prefixes just alter the form, these negations directly change the meaning of the words they are applied to. The term prefix is formed by combining the root word *fix*, which means to fasten or position, with the prefix *pre-*, which indicates *before*. It literally means “*to place before*.”

Like other affixes, prefixes can be either derivational, which creates a new word with a new semantic meaning and occasionally a different lexical category, or inflectional, which creates a new form of the word with the same core meaning and same lexical category (but playing a different role in the sentence). Prefixes, like all other affixes, are frequently bound morphemes.

In English, there are no inflectional prefixes; instead, suffixes are employed. The two Latin-derived components of the term prefix are *fix*, which means “attach,” and “pre-“, which means “before.” Because prefixes are tied morphemes, they cannot stand on their own. If a prefix is made up of letters, it cannot be a word in and of itself. The process of adding a prefix to a word is a common approach for English speakers to generate new words.

Suffix

A suffix, also known as a postfix, is an affix that follows the word stem in linguistics. A suffix is a letter or group of letters that is affixed to the end of the fundamental form of a word or root. Suffixes can be used to generate new words or as inflectional endings. The Latin root of the term suffix means “to fasten beneath.”

Examples include verb endings, which define verb conjugation, and case endings, which indicate the grammatical case of nouns or adjectives. Suffixes are known as *affirmatives*, specifically in the study of Semitic languages, because they can change the form of the words.

Suffixes and endings are different concepts in Indo-European studies (see Proto-Indo-European root). Suffixes can convey lexical or grammatical information.

In English, there are primarily two categories of suffixes:

Derivational, such as when an adjective is given the suffix “-ly” to create an adverb, denoting the word’s kind.

Inflectional, such as the adding of the suffix “-s” to a noun to make it plural, which reveals information about the grammatical behavior of the word.

It’s common to refer to an inflectional suffix as a *desinence*, otherwise a grammatical suffix. Inflection changes the grammatical properties of a word within its syntactic category

Class-changing derivation and *class-preserving derivation* are two categories of derivative suffixes. A word’s stem is followed by an affix known as a suffix, sometimes known as an ending. Verb endings, which determine the conjugation of verbs, and case endings, which indicate the grammatical case of nouns or adjectives, are typical examples.

Infix

A form of affix known as an infix has a somewhat different function and is far less frequent in English. Instead of being added to the start or end of a base word, an infix is inserted directly into the base word.

An infix is a letter that is inserted into a word; these are uncommon in English, however *cupful* can be made plural by adding the letter *s* as an infix to make *cupsful*; infixes occasionally appear in satirical inventions like *absobloodylutely*.

Inflectional Affixes of English

A general grammar procedure called inflection combines words and affixes—always suffixes in English—to create different grammatical forms of words.

A derivational affix is typically located closer to the root than an inflectional affix, which results in a predictable, nonidiosyncratic change of meaning. An inflectional affix expresses a grammatical contrast that is required for the word class of its stem in a particular grammatical context but does not change the word class of its stem.

In English, there are eight inflectional affixes. They are grammatical affixes that do not change the classification of the word. They are always using derivational affixes.

The third person singular present *-s*, the past tense marker *-ed*, the continuous marker *-ing*, the past participle *-en*, the plural marker *-s*, the possessive marker *'s*, the comparative suffix *-er*, and the superlative suffix *-est* are the eight inflectional affixes in English.

Derivational Affixes

Inflection's opposite is derivation. It entails modifying the word's root or stem by appending one or more affixes. New words are derived when this is done. The distinction between class-maintaining and class-preserving procedures is frequently made within derivation. A new term with different word class is created through class switching. (For instance, *gentle* (adj), *gentleness* (noun), and *softly* (adverb)); but class-preserving results in the creation of a new term without altering the class. A derivational affix is one that is utilized to create (derive) another word from another. The derived word often forms different word class than the source word. A derivational affix, as opposed to an inflectional affix:

- is not a required group of affixes,
- usually occurs closer to the root,
- is more significant, and
- is more likely to produce a form with a slightly peculiar meaning.

There is no theoretical upper limit to the number of derivational affixes in English, which now has over 60 frequent ones.

Derivational affixes, in contrast to inflectional affixes, can alter the word class of the thing they are applied to. Derivational affixes are inner, closer to the stem, while inflectional affixes are

outer, farther from the stem, if both inflectional and derivational affixes are utilized. For instance, resignation + ation + s = *resignations*, while fear + en + ed = *fearful*

Types of Derivational Affixes

The two categories of derivational affixes are class-changing and class-preserving. Derivational affixes that modify word class are known as class-changing affixes. As a result, the adjective *attainable* is made up of the verb *attain* plus the suffix *-able*. Class-preserving derivational affixes, however, simply alter the meaning of the word and do not alter the word's class. For example, the term *adult* and the suffix *-hood* combine to generate the abstract noun *adulthood*, which is no longer a concrete noun. When class-changing affixes are attached to word stems, the word's class is instantaneously changed, allowing it to function variously as a verb, a noun, an adverb, or an adjective. Derivational affixes thereby control or dictate the word class of the stem. As an illustration, nouns can come from verbs or adjectives, adjectives can come from both verbs and nouns, adverbs can come from either adjectives or nouns, and verbs can come from either nouns or adjectives. Suffixes predominate among English derivations that change classes.

Class-Preserving Derivational Affixes

The employment of derivational morphemes results in the creation of new words from the use of preexisting ones. They could be suffixes or prefixes. Think about how the addition of the prefixes *re-* and *dis-* might change the root morpheme *organize*. The newly derived terms, "*re-organize*" and "*dis-organize*," are verbs just like their newly derived roots, "*organize*," which is a verb. The prefix's insertion has had no impact on the word class. Therefore, these derivational prefixes are referred to be class-preserving.

Class-preserving derivations influence the meaning of the stem but do not change the class of the stem to which they are appended. Class-preserving derivations are prefixes and suffixes as opposed to class-changing derivations, which are mostly suffixes.

English derivational prefixes, unlike derivational suffixes, frequently do not alter the base's lexical category (and are so called class-preserving prefixes). As a result, both the word *do*, which is made up of a single morpheme, and the word *redo*, which is made up of the prefix *re-* and the base root *do*, are verbs. Examples of class-preserving suffixes are *-ry*, *-age*, *-ate*, *-cy*, *-dom*, *-ee*, *-eer*, *-ful*, *-hood*, *-ic*, *-ism*, *-ship*, *-ster*, *-ure*, etc.

Class-Changing Derivational Affixes

Now think about what occurs when suffixes are added.

Recall how the suffix *-ation* can change the basic verb *organize* to form the word *organiz-ation*. The freshly created word is a noun this time. Similar to how the word “*organizer*” created by adding the suffix “*-er*” is also a noun. These suffixes are class-changing because they have changed the word class of the word to which they are affixed. In most cases, adding the suffix *-ise* turns an adjective into a verb instead of a noun, as in the case of *private* (adjective) becoming *private-ise* (verb), and *nation* (noun) becoming *nation-al* (adjective).

In order to create abstract nouns from verbs, adjectives, and nouns, nominal suffixes are frequently used. These abstract nouns can signify actions, outcomes, or other related notions, as well as attributes, qualities, and other things of the sort. Person nouns of various types are derived from a sizable additional group of nominal suffixes. The semantic domains of various suffixes frequently overlap, showing that nearly every suffix can express more than one meaning. These meanings are frequently expanded to additional, related senses.

The following are noun-derivational affixes, commonly known as nominalizers:

Verb	Affix	Noun
act	-or	actor
assist	-ant	assistant
betray	-al	betrayal
brag	-art	braggart
defend	-ce	defence
depart	-ure	departure
dictate	-ion	dictation
disturb	-ance	disturbance
employ	-ee	employee
enquire (BE) or inquiry	-y	enquiry (BE) OR inquiry
exist	-ence	existence
juxtapose	-ition	juxtaposition
neutralize	-ation	neutralization
require	-ment	requirement
shrink	-age	shrinkage
teach	-er	teacher

Adjective	Affix	Noun
absent	-ee	absentee
alert	-ness	alertness
arrogant	-ance	arrogance
brilliant	-ancy	brilliance
cynic	-ism	cynicism
delicate	-acy	delicacy
similar	-ity	similarity
social	-ist	socialist
social	-te	socialite
true	-th	truth
wise	-dom	wisdom

Verbalizers, or verb-derivational affixes, are employed to create verbs from other classes of words. Although verbs are employed to form other types of words, they are difficult to form from other components of speech. The following derivational affixes combine nouns and adjectives to form verbs.

Noun	Affix	Verb
able	en-	enable
Adjective	Affix	Verb
character	-ize	characterize
head	be-	behead
legal	-ize	legalize
pure	-ify	purify
short	-en	shorten
terror	-fy	terrify
title	en-	entitle

Noun	Affix	Adjective
anonym	-ous	anonymous
aqua	-ic	aquatic
black	-en	blacken
child	-ish	childish
China	-ese	Chinese
cloud	-y	cloudy
day	-ly	daily
deceit	-ful	deceitful
life	-like	lifelike
passion	-ate	passionate
picture	-esque	picturesque
remorse	-less	remorseless

revolution	-ary	revolutionary
suburb	-an	suburban
voice	-al	vocal
wound	-ed	wounded

Adjective derivational affixes, also known as *adjectivizers*, are employed to generate adjectives from nouns rather than verbs.

Verb	Affix	Adjective
adapt	-ive	adaptive
bother	-some	bothersome
change	-able	changeable
confide	-ent	confident
sense	-ory	sensory

Adverb-derivational affixes, also known as *adverbializers*, are affixes that assist generate adverbs from adjectives rather than nouns.

Adjective	Affix	Adverb
clock	-wise	clockwise
constant	-ly	constantly
heaven	-wards	heavenwards
Noun	Affix	Adverb
rare	-ly	rarely
river	-ward	riverward
shore	a-	ashore

Words' Derivation from One Grammatical Class to Another

Let's now examine how the addition of the above-mentioned suffixes might transform words into another grammatical category:

Changing Verbs into Nouns

The noun-forming suffixes are attached to the verb in order to create new words and create nouns from verbs.

a) *-ment*

This suffix creates action nouns that denote processes or outcomes from (mostly) verbs, with a strong preference for monosyllable or disyllabic base words with emphasis on the last syllable (e.g. *assessment, endorsement, involvement, treatment*).

Some examples are:

Verb	Noun
abridge	abridgement
amend	amendment
argue	argument
defile	defilement
detach	detachment
embellish	embellishment
incite	incitement
resent	resentment

b) *-ion/-tion*

This Latinate suffix contains three allomorphs: when combined with a verb in the *-ify* form, the verbal suffix and *-ion* produce the word “*ification*” (personification). In all other cases, we find the allomorph *-ation*, and the *-ion* when it is related to a verb ending in *-ate* (followed by a change of the base-final consonant from [t] to [s], hyphenation) (*starvation*, *colonization*). Because all *-ion* derivatives have their major emphasis on the penultimate syllable phonologically, *-ion* is among the group of suffixes that might result in a shift in stress. A derivative ending in *-ion* refers to an occurrence or a process’s output. As a result, verbal bases are by far the most common, but there are also a sizable number of forms where *-ation* is affixed to nouns directly without a verb in *-ate* in between. These forms are mostly seen in scientific discourse, where bases are words that refer to chemicals or other substances (e.g. *expoxide* - *epoxidation*, *sediment* - *sedimentation*).

Verb	Noun
absorb	absorption
accumulate	accumulation
adapt	adaptation
adopt	adoption
collect	collection
contend	contention
destroy	destruction
devote	devotion
intend	intention
obstruct	obstruction
pretend	pretension
recognize	recognition
repress	repression
resolve	resolution

Verbs that finish in *-ate* remove the *e* and take a *-ion* instead.

Verb	Noun
illustrate	<i>illustration</i>
meditate	<i>meditation</i>
demonstrate	<i>demonstration</i>
pollinate	<i>pollination</i>
enumerate	<i>enumeration</i>
stagnate	<i>stagnation</i>

c) *-ation*

Some verbs ending in *-ise* receive the suffix *-ation*. The final *e* is dropped before the *-ation* is added. Here are several examples:

Verb	Noun
authorize	authorization
civilize	civilization
improvise	improvisation
polarize	polarization

Others are:

Verb	Noun
afforest	afforestation
crown	coronation
deprive	deprivation
derive	derivation
divine	divination
fix	fixation
inhale	inhalation

Continuing with the *-ation* theme, if the verb ends in *ke*, the *ke* is replaced by *c* before the suffix:

Verb	Noun
convoke	convocation
evoke	evocation
invoke	invocation
provoke	provocation
revoke	revocation

Verbs ending in *-ain* or *-aim* lose the *i* and take *-ation*:

Verb	Noun
abstain	abstention
declaim	declamation
entertain	entertainment
exclaim	exclamation
explain	explanation
proclaim	proclamation

d) *-ication*

Some verbs with *-ify* endings lose the *y* and replace it with *-ication*:

Verb	Noun
beatify	beatification
gasify	gasification
sanctify	sanctification
solidify	solidification

Exceptions:

Verb	Noun
crucify	crucifixion
liquefy	liquefaction (not *liquidification)
putrefy (not *putrify)	putrefaction

e) *-ition*

-ition is added to verbs that finish in *-ish*. The letters *sh* are removed and replaced with *-ition*.

Verb	Noun
abolish	abolition
admonish	admonition
demolish	demolition

Different suffixes are used for other *-ish* ending words. Here are several examples:

Verb	Noun
banish	banishment
embellish	embellishment
furnish	furniture/furnishing

-ition can also be added to verbs that finish in *-it*.

Verb	Noun
exhibit	exhibition
fruit	fruition
inhibit	inhibition
prohibit	prohibition

Some *-it* ending words are suffixed with *-ssion* (to be discussed later).

f) **-ution**

The ve in verbs ending in -olve is substituted by -ution.

Verb	Noun
absolve	absolution
devolve	devolution
evolve	evolution
resolve	resolution
revolve	revolution

g) **-sion**

Some words ending in *-ise* are given the suffix *-sion*, with the *e* deleted.

Verb	Noun
excise	excision
revise	revision
supervise	supervision

Some words ending in *-de* lose this ending to produce nouns with *-sion*. Here are several examples:

Verb	Noun
collide	collision
conclude	conclusion
decide	decision
divide	division
evade	evasion
extrude	extrusion
invade	invasion
persuade	persuasion
provide	provision

The suffix *-sion* is also applied to verbs that end in *t*. To make noun, the *t* is deleted and replaced by *-sion*.

Verb	Noun
avert	aversion
convert	conversion
divert	diversion
invert	inversion
revert	reversion

h) Double s suffix *-ssion*

This happens with verbs that end in *-ee* or *-ede*.

Verb	Noun
accede	accession
concede	concession
intercede	intercession
proceed	procession
secede	secession
supersede	supersession

Some verbs ending in *-it* also attract *-ssion*.

Verb	Noun
emit	emission
omit	omission
remit	remission/remittance
transmit	transmission

i) *-ant, -ent*

Count nouns with the suffix *-ant* relate to people (typically in technical or legal speech, cf. *applicant, defendant, disclaimant*) or things involved in biological, chemical, or physical processes (*attractant, dispersant, etchant, suppressant*). The majority of bases are Latinate verbs.

-ant:

Verb	Noun
celebrate	celebrant
coagulate	coagulant
confide	confidant
depend	dependant
lubricate	lubricant
migrate	migrant
occupy	occupant
serve	servant

–ent:

Verb	Noun
adhere	adherent
antecede	antecedent
correspond	correspondent
deter	deterrent
precede	precedent
preside	president
receive	recipient
study	student

j) **–ance, –ence**

There are times when these two suffixes are ambiguous. Sometimes spellers struggle to recall which of the two to use. Verbs with a final *e* drop the *e* when adding *–ance* is frequently used with other verbs when there is no final *e*. When the suffix *–ance* is added to verbs, action nouns such as *absorption*, *riddance*, and *retardance* are generated. The ending is closely related to *–cy/–ce*, which attaches well to adjectives ending in *–ant/–ent*. As a result, it is feasible to discern whether a derivative, such as *dependence*, has two suffixes (*depend-ent-cy*) or just one (*depend-ency*). The following question is whether *–ance* (and its variants) always contain two suffixes, implying that all action nominals are descended from adjectives, which are descended from verbs. We would only find *–ance* nominals if there were comparable *–ant* adjectives, according to our technique. This is clearly not the case, as demonstrated by *riddance* (**riddant*) and *furthering* (**furtherant*), therefore we can deduce the presence of an *independent*.

There are several doublets documented, such as *dependence*, *dependency*, or *expectance*, *expectancy*, though the distribution of the various variants is not entirely obvious. The doublets' meanings appear to be similar at times and slightly different at others. However, it appears that all forms ending in *–ance/–ence* have been there for a very long time and that *–ance/–ence* formations are often considered to be deverbal, whilst *–ancy/–ency* formations are commonly understood to be de-adjectival.

*–ance nouns***Verbs with final *e***

Verb	Noun
dominate	dominance
grieve	grievance
ignore	ignorance
reassure	reassurance
remonstrate	remonstrance
tolerate	tolerance

*–ance nouns***Verbs without final e**

Verb	Noun
abbey	abeyance
attend	attendance
clear	clearance
maintain	maintenance
perform	performance
react	reactance

*–ence nouns***Verbs with final e**

Verb	Noun
adhere	adherence
coincide	coincidence
condole	condolence
confide	confidence
precede	precedence
subserve	subservience

*–ence nouns***Verbs without final e**

Verb	Noun
abhor	abhorrence
absent	absence
infer	inference
obey	obedience
offend	offence
prominent	prominence

Adjectives can also be converted to nouns using the suffixes *–ance* and *–ence*.

k) **–ism, –ysis**

–ism: Derivatives of this category describe the associated concepts state, condition, attitude, system of views, or theory, as in *blondism*, *Parkinsonism*, *conservatism*, *revisionism*, and *Marxism*, respectively, by forming abstract nouns from other nouns and adjectives. These suffixes are commonly used on adjectives and nouns. They are sometimes used in the conversion of verbs to nouns:

Verb	Noun
criticise	criticism
dogmatise	dogmatism
plagiarise	plagiarism

In scientific jargon, the suffix *–ysis* is commonly found:

Verb	Noun
analyse	analysis
electrolyse	electrolysis

l) **–al**

Arrival, *overthrowal*, *recital*, *referral*, and *renewal* are examples of verbs that take *–al* to generate abstract nouns signifying an activity or the effect of an action. The last syllable of all nominal base words is stressed the most. Examples of *–al* nouns derived from verbs include:

Verb	Noun
acquit	acquittal
arouse	arousal
avow	avowal
betray	betrayal
rebut	rebuttal
rehearse	rehearsal
withdraw	withdrawal

The *e* is eliminated where the verb concludes with an *e*. The *t* is duplicated where it ends with *t*.

m) **–age**

This suffix is derived from nouns that indicate an activity (or its effect), such as *coverage*, *leakage*, as well as nouns that denote a collective entity or number, such as *area*, *voltage*, and *yardage*. Because of the inherent ambiguity of some coinages, the definition might be extended to cover locales, such as *orphanage*. Base words can be verbal or nominal, and they are frequently monosyllabic.

- Age is usually linked to nouns, although it can also be attached to verbs to generate nouns:

Verb	Noun
cleave	cleavage
cover	coverage
post	postage
use	usage
waste	wastage

The *e* ending of the verb has been omitted.

n) **-ry, -ery**

Formations in *-(e)ry* relate to sites that have some sort of relationship to what is signified by the base. More specific meanings such as “place where a specific activity is carried out” or “place where a specific article or service is available” could be proposed (cf. *bakery, brewery, fishery, pottery or cakery, carwashery, eatery*), but examples such as *mousery, cannery, rabbitry* speak for an unspecified meaning, which is then fleshed out for each derivative based on the meaning of the base.

-(e)ry derivatives can also suggest collectivities (as in *confectionery, cutlery, machinery*) or activities (as in *summitry* “having numerous political peaks,” *crookery* “foul actions”). The suffix *-ry* turns a few verbs into nouns. The two suffixes are typically added to nouns. They can be attached to verbs to generate nouns in the following ways:

Verb	Noun
bake	bakery
brew	brewery
hatch	hatchery
husband	husbandry
launder	laundry
mimic	mimicry
revel	revelry
water	watery

o) **-ure**

A few verbs are transformed into nouns by the suffix *-ure*. Verbs ending in consonants simply take *-ure*, whereas those ending in *e* drop the *e* before *-ure*:

Verb	Noun
erase	erasure
fail	failure
forfeit	forfeiture
invest	investiture
legislate	legislature
pose	posture
proceed	procedure
seize	seizure

–ure is also used for a few adjectives, but mostly for nouns.

p) **–acy**

The suffix –acy is used to turn some verbs to nouns:

Verb	Noun
advocate	advocacy
conspire	conspiracy

The e ending of the verb has been omitted. Suffixes are also added to nouns and adjectives.

q) **Action Suffixes**

These are suffixes that describe people’s deeds or occupations, or the uses of things. They contain the suffixes *–er*, *–or*, *–ant*, and *–ist* (or *–yst*). We also have the uncommon suffix *–ar*. Given that its derivatives typically describe creatures who are active or voluntary participants in an event, the suffix *–er* is closely related to the suffix *–ee* (e.g. *teacher*, *singer*, *writer* etc.). However, this is only a subclass of *–er* derivatives, and there are several forms with a wide range of meanings. Aside from nouns denoting action-performers, words denoting things employed in an activity include *diner*, *lounger*, *trainer*, and *winner* (in the sense of a “winning shot”). Furthermore, the suffix “*–er*” is used to generate person nouns that indicate place of origin or habitation (e.g. *Londoner*, *New Yorker*, *Highlander*, and *New Englander*).

Given this diversity, it appears acceptable to classify the meaning of *–er* as somewhat ambiguous, i.e., “person or object having something to do with X.” The interactions of the base and suffix meanings, as well as subsequent deductions based on general knowledge, would eventually lead to more specific interpretations of individual formations. Although *er* is commonly regarded as a deverbial suffix, there are numerous varieties (not simply resident names) formed from nouns (such as *sealer*, *whaler*, *noser*, and *souther*), numerals (such as *fiver* and *tenner*), or even phrases (*four-wheeler*, *fourthgrader*).

The orthographic variant *-or* is most commonly found in Latinate bases that end in /s/ or /t/, such as *conductor*, *oscillator*, and *compressor*. Nouns ending in *-ar* can refer to biological, chemical, or physical processes or to individuals (usually in technical or legal contexts; see (*application*, *defendant*, and *disclaimer*) (*attractant*, *dispersant*, *etchant*, *suppressant*). The majority of bases are verbs in Latin. Most nouns that characterize humans end in *-ist*, which is derived from adjectival and nominal bases (*ballonist*, *careerist*, *fantasist*, *minimalist*). All nouns that end in “ism” that denote beliefs, theories, or ideologies have potential counterparts that end in “ist.” The definition of *-ist* is an unspecified “person associated with X,” with the specific meaning of the derivative depending on the meaning of the base and additional inference. A *careerist* is someone who is primarily concerned with their job, a *balloonist* is someone who ascends in a balloon, and a *fundamentalist* is someone who believes in or supports fundamentalism. Examples include: *-er*.

Verb	Noun
betray	betrayer
carry	carrier
cool	cooler
defend	defender
inform	informer
magnify	magnifier
send	sender
spell	speller
teach	teacher
write	writer

-or

Verb	Noun
act	actor
convey	conveyor
decorate	decorator
mediate	mediator
sail	sailor
vend	vendor

-ant

Verb	Noun
aspire	aspirant
celebrate	celebrant
depend	dependant
enter	entrant
inform	informant
inhabit	inhabitant
pollute	pollutant

-ist, -yst

Verb	Noun
anaesthetise	anesthetist
apologise	apologist
catalyse	catalyst
dogmatise	dogmatist
dramatise	dramatist
pacify	pacifist
plagiarise	plagiarist

-ar

Verb	Noun
beg	beggar
lie	liar

r) -ing, -ee, -and

The final groups of verb-to-noun suffixes are *-ing*, and *-ee*. A verb's present participle is sometimes employed as a noun ending in *-ing*.

His singing and dancing were well-received.

He has a massive following as a leader.

The project was successfully launching.

This deverbal suffix denotes processes (*begging, running, sleeping*) or outcomes (*building, wrapping, stuffing*). The suffix is unique among derivational suffixes in that it is predominantly utilized as a verbal inflectional suffix in the formation of present participles. Because *-ing* can be attached to almost any verb, examples of relevant derivatives abound.

-ee:

The meaning of this suffix is rather obvious. It derives nouns representing sentient creatures who participate in an event as non-volitional participants (so-called 'episodic *-ee*,' see Barker (1998) for a comprehensive examination). Thus, *employee* refers to someone who is employed, *biographee* refers to someone who is the topic of a biography, and *standee* refers to someone who is made to stand (on a bus, for example). Because the referents of *-ee* derivatives must be sentient, an amputee can only be someone who has lost a limb, not the limb that has been severed. Because of the event-related, episodic semantics, verbal bases predominate, but nominal bases are not uncommon (e.g. *festschрифtee, pickpocketee*). *-ee* is a phonologically auto-stressed suffix, which means it belongs to the small class of suffixes that draw the main stress of the derivation. Base words that end in the verbal suffix *-ate* are frequently shortened and lose their terminal rime.

Verb	Noun
address	addressee
employ	employee
pay	payee
vend	vendee

–and:

This has a narrow range of applications. A *graduand* is an undergraduate who is about to graduate. An *ordinand* is a person who is going to be ordained as a priest.

Conversion of Verbs to Adjectives

Adjectives are formed by adding the suffixes *–able*, *–ible*, *–ous*, *–ive*, *–ory*, *–al*, *–ant*, *–ent*, *–some*, *–f* to verbs

i. *–able*

Some verbs with consonant endings accept *able* without modification, however if the fundamental verb ends in *–ate*, this end is eliminated and substituted with *able*:

Verb	Adjective
abominate	abominable
accept	acceptable
appreciate	appreciable
book	bookable
calculate	calculable
comfort	comfortable
demonstrate	demonstrable
educate	educable
favor	favourable
honour	honourable

The *e* is preserved if the basic verb finishes in *ce*, but if it ends in *y* after a consonant, the *y* is replaced by *i*. Here are several examples:

Verb	Adjective
descry	describable
enforce	enforceable
pity	pitiable
pronounce	pronounceable
rely	reliable
trace	traceable

However, the rule is not robber-stamped because apply is applicable rather than **applicabile*. The *e* is frequently deleted if the basic verb ends in *e* after a consonant or after *s*:

Verb	Adjective
admire	admirable
debate	debatable
move	movable/moveable
prove	provable
use	usable

The adjective for *despise* is however *despicable*. Finally, if the basic verb ends in *y* after a vowel, the *y* is retained:

Verb	Adjective
convey	conveyable
essay	essay-able
pay	payable
play	playable

ii. *-ible*

The number of verbs that take the suffix *-ible* is restricted. It is frequently drawn to nouns. When added to verbs ending in *e*, the *e* is dropped; when added to verbs ending in *t* or *d*, the last letter is dropped and substituted with *-sible* or *-ssible*. Here are several examples:

Verb	Adjective
admit	admissible
collapse	collapsible
comprehend	comprehensible
defend	defensible
force	forcible
omit	omissible
reprehend	reprehensible
reverse	reversible

Among the exceptions are:

Verb	Adjective
controvert	controvertible
resist	resistible

iii. *-ous*

A few verbs can have the suffix *-ous* added to them to generate adjectives:

Verb	Adjective
cumber	cumbrous/cumbersome
disaster	disastrous
pity	piteous
ponder	ponderous
pretend	pretentious

iv. *-ory*

Only a few verbs can have this suffix added to make adjectives:

Verb	Adjective
declaim	declamatory
exclaim	exclamatory
explain	explanatory
inhibit	inhibitory
retaliate	retaliatory

The *i* in *ai* has been lost in these nouns.

v. *-ive*

Many verbs can have the suffix *-ive* added to them to form adjectives. Words ending in *e* drop the *e* before the suffix, but words ending in consonants simply take the suffix:

Verb	Adjective
construct	constructive
cumulate	cumulative
cure	curative
decorate	decorative
express	expressive
indicate	indicative
instruct	instructive
possess	possessive
prevent	preventive
restore	restorative
speculate	speculative

Some nouns have *d* substituted by *s*, while others have the suffix *-ative*:

Verb	Adjective
affirm	affirmative
conclude	conclusive

confirm	confirmative
decide	decisive
divide	divisive
exclude	exclusive
include	inclusive
preserve	preservative
represent	representative

Other instances include:

Verb	Adjective
apprehend	apprehensive
comprehend	comprehensive
defend	defensive
offend	offensive

The *d* in these nouns has been dropped, and the suffix *-sive* has been added.

Verb	Adjective
admit	admissive
permit	permissive
submit	submissive

The *t* in these words has been dropped, and the suffix *-ssive* has been added.

vi. *-al*

The adjectives created with *-al* from verbs are as follows:

Verb	Adjective
criticize	critical
pontificate	pontifical

This suffix is frequently used to convert nouns to adjectives.

vii. *-ant, -ent*

These suffixes, like those used to form nouns from verbs, can also be employed to form adjectives:

Verb	Adjective
decay	decadent
defy	defiant
deliquesce	deliquescent
effervesce	effervescent
please	pleasant
repent	repentant

vii. *-some, -ful*

Some adjectives that finish in some verbs are as follows:

Verb	Adjective
cumber	cumbersome
fear	fearsome
grue	gruesome
quarrel	quarrelsome
tire	tiresome

Only a few verbs have the suffix *-ful*. It is more commonly connected to nouns to make adjectives. It is appended to verbs in the following places:

Verb	Adjective
mourn	mournful
revenge	vengeful

Conversion of Adjectives to Nouns

The following suffixes are used to convert adjectives to nouns: *-ness, -ity, -ion, -acy, -ery, -ry, -ment, -ism, -ance, -ancy, -ence, -ency, and -escence*.

viii. *-ness*

Adjective	Noun
beastly	beastliness
busy	business
happy	happiness
saintly	saintliness
sprightly	sprightliness

In these words, the letter *y* has been replaced by the letter *i*.

ix. –ity

Words in this morphological category are nouns that denote qualities, conditions, or traits and are typically derived from Latinate adjectives (e.g. *curiosity*, *productivity*, *profundity*, *solidity*). Aside from the compositional meaning just described, many *–ity* derivatives have become lexicalized, that is, they have become permanently incorporated into the mental lexicons of speakers, often adopting idiosyncratic meanings, such as *antiquity* “state of being antique” or “ancient time,” *curiosity* “quality of being curious,” and “curious thing.” All adjectives ending in the suffixes *–able*, *–al*, and *–ic*, as well as the phonetic string [id], can accept the nominalizing suffix *–ity* (*readability*, *formality*, *erraticity*, *solidity*). Some nouns have the suffix *–ity* added without any change. In several circumstances, the last *e* of the basic adjective is omitted:

Adjective	Noun
agile	agility
diverse	diversity
ductile	ductility
fluid	fluidity
humid	humidity
infinite	infinity
infirm	infirmity
morbid	morbidity
normal	normality
nude	nudity
plural	plurality
profane	profanity
pure	purity
senior	seniority

x. –ion

Several adjectives are drawn to the suffix *–ion* to generate nouns:

Adjective	Noun
abject	abjection
contrite	contrition
discreet	discretion
dissolve	dissolution
resolve	resolution

xi. *-acy, -ery, -ry, -ment*

Only a few adjectives attract these prefixes, resulting in nouns. They are as follows: *-acy, -ry, -ment*.

Adjective	Noun
accurate	accuracy
better	betterment
brave	bravery
delicate	delicacy
green	greenery
merry	merriment

xii. *-ism*

-ism is most commonly used to convert nouns to nouns. It can, however, be used with a few adjectives to make nouns

Adjective	Noun
altruistic	altruism
American	Americanism
archaic	archaism
colloquial	colloquialism
monetary	monetarism
mystic	mysticism
true	truism
witty	witticism

xiii. *-ance, -ancy, -ence, -ency*

These four suffixes are frequently used to transform adjectives to nouns. Here are several examples: *-ant* to *-ance*

Adjective	Noun
abundant	abundance
attendant	attendance
dominant	dominance
elegant	elegance
relevant	relevance

–ant to –ancy

Adjective	Noun
constant	constancy
expectant	expectancy
hesitant	hesitancy
infant	infancy
vacant	vacancy

–ent to –ence

Adjective	Noun
corpulent	corpulence
prominent	prominence
reticent	reticence
subsistent	subsistence

–ent to –ency

Adjective	Noun
absorbent	absorbency
clement	clemency
consistent	consistency
fluent	fluency

xiv. *–escence*

Adjectives that finish in *–escent* become nouns that end in *–escence*. Here are several examples:

Adjective	Noun
Acquiescent	acquiescence
Coalescent	coalescence
Deliquescent	deliquescence
Fluorescent	fluorescence

xv. *–iety*

Adjective	Noun
anxious	anxiety
proper	propriety
sober	sobriety
various	variety

Conversion of Nouns to Adjectives

The suffixes used to turn nouns to adjectives are: *-y*, *-ly*, *-ous*, *-ish*, *-ic*, *-ics*, *-ical*, *-ary*, *-ar*, *-less*, *-full*, *-al*, *-ial*, *-eal*, *-ate*, *-ine*, *-ean*, *-ian*, *-ese*, *-en*, *-esque*, *-able*, *-ible*, *-iac*.

xvi. *-y*, *-ly*

Nouns and adjectives are given the suffix *-ly*. With base nouns signifying people, *-ly* usually means “in the manner of X” or “like an X,” as in *brotherly*, *daughterly*, *fatherly*, and *womanly*. Other typical derivatives have bases that represent temporal ideas (e.g., *half-hourly*, *daily*, *monthly*) or directions (*easterly*).

Noun	Adjective
beast	beastly
day	daily
friend	friendly
haze	hazy
king	kingly
lace	lacy
mother	motherly
sauce	saucy

xvii. *-ish*

Adjective	Noun
book	bookish
boy	boyish
fever	feverish
fiend	fiendish

xviii. *-ous*

In addition to converting verbs to adjectives and adjectives to nouns, *-ous* can be used to convert nouns to adjectives. Here are several examples:

Noun	Adjective
disaster	disastrous
glamour	glamorous
glory	glorious
mischievous	mischievous
number	numerous
peril	perilous
pity	piteous
poison	poisonous

xix. *-ic, -ics, -ical*

Noun	Adjective
aesthete	aesthetic
athlete	athletic
drama	dramatic
geography	geographic
giant	gigantic
harmony	harmonic
hero	heroic
melody	melodic

The suffix *-ic* is pluralized when used to particular studies. Adjectives produced from these nouns omit the s and increase the suffix to *-ical*. Here are several examples:

Noun	Adjective
Acoustic	acoustical
Economics	economical
Ethics	ethical
Mathematics	mathematical
Physics	physical
Politics	political

xx. *-ary, -ar*

Noun	Adjective
budget	budgetary
diet	dietary
element	elementary
molecule	molecular
nucleus	nuclear
spatula	spatular

xxi. *-ful, -less*

Noun	Adjective
art	artless
care	careful
doubt	doubtful
fear	fearful
sin	sinless
taste	tasteless

Other adjectives derived from nouns include:

Noun	Adjective
adamant	adamantine
alkali	alkaline
Christ	Christian
crystal	crystalline
earth	earthen
exception	exceptional
fashion	fashionable
gold	golden
honour	honourable
incident	incidental
race	racial
remedy	remedial
substance	substantial
verb	verbal

Conversion of Nouns to Verbs

Some nouns can be turned into verbs by adding the following suffixes: *-en* (or *-n*), *-ify* (or *-fy*), *-ise* (or *-ize*), and *-ate* are all verbs.

xxii. *-en* (or *-n*)

Noun	Verb
height	heighten
length	lengthen
strength	strengthen

xxiii. *-ify* (or *-fy*)

Noun	Verb
beauty	beautify
example	exemplify
stupor	stupefy

xiv. *-ise*, *-ate*

-ise

Noun	Verb
carbon	carbonize
idol	idolize
vapour	vapourise

–ate

Noun	Verb
carbon	carbonate
motion	motivate

Conversion of Adjectives to Verbs

The suffix *-en*, or the prefix *en-*, is a popular suffix for this purpose, as in:

Adjective	Verb
black	blacken
bright	brighten
dear	endear
deep	deepen
large	enlarge
loose	loosen
noble	ennoble
rich	enrich
tight	tighten
white	whiten

Conclusion

This study demonstrated the importance of affixation in the process of word formation in the English language, as well as how class-changing derivational affixes change the grammatical category of the word by producing a new term. The collection of class-altering prefixes and suffixes is endless. Some prefixes and suffixes are just inflections that are added to words to pluralize, change tense, or denote comparative and superlative adjective forms. Others, as we've seen, are class-altering suffixes.

Mastery of these affixes will lead to proficiency in English spelling, writing, and speaking.

As a result, it is critical to recognize root words and affixes, as well as correctly use and generate them in sentences. Although they appear small at first glance, affixes play an important part in the construction of English words. While they keep the word class in some circumstances, they radically modify it in others.

References and Bibliography

Affix - Wikipedia

Affixation - Stela Manov

Aliti, A., & Iseni, A. (2014). THE CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ENGLISH-ING CLAUSE AS DIRECT OBJECT AND ITS ALBANIAN CORRESPONDENTS. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(14).

Aliti, A., Iseni, A., & Rexhepi, N. The Contrastive Analysis of the English–ING Clause as Prepositional Complement and Its Albanian Correspondents.

Bright, W. (ed.) (1992). *International Encyclopedia of Linguistics*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Crystal D. (1997). *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language*. Second Edition. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Derivational Affix - <https://glossary.sil.org/term/derivational-affix>

Frank, M. (1980). *Writing as Thinking: A Guided process Approach*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc.

Hornby, A. S. *Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary of Current English*. 7th Edition. Oxford University Press.

Inflectional Affixes of English - <http://lgzsoldos.blogspot.com/2011/03/inflectional-affixes-of-english.html>

Johnson, B. E. (1992). *Doing It Right: Improving College Learning Skills*. Toronto- Canada: Heath and Company.

Marchand, H. (1969). *The categories and types of present-day English word-formation: A synchronic-diachronic approach*. Munich: Beck

Metacalfe, J. E. and Astle, C. (MCMXCV). *Correct English*. England: Clarion

Morphemes, roots and affixes, 28 October 2011-
<http://www.unizd.hr/portals/36/kolegiji/morphology/morphology%203.pdf>

Nida, E. (1949). *Morphology: The descriptive analysis of words*. Ann Arbor: Univ. of Michigan Press.

Plag, Ingo, *Word-formation in English*, Cambridge University Press Series 'Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics', Draft version of September 27, 2002

Prefix – Wikipedia

Types of Derivational Affixes - <https://studfiles.net/preview/5809158/page:17/>

What Are Affixes, Prefixes, and Suffixes in English Grammar? <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-affix-grammar-1689071>

Xhelili, V. (2022). A WORD AND ITS RELATIVES: DERIVATION IN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 11(7), 93-108.

.